

WATER IN HINDU URBAN ARCHITECTURE

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On the first day of the Tamil month of Adi (July/August) the sluices of the anicut on the Cauvery are opened, and the river waters, heavily swollen after the first monsoon rains, are released to irrigate the paddy fields. This is the beginning of the agricultural season, celebrated as a great festival by the peasant population who congregate from far and wide on the ghats near Srirangam. They shout: 'The Lady has arrived!', 'Congratulations to the Lady!', and in the evening of that day the priests from the Srirangam temple come to the ghats, carrying Lord Raganathan¹ in procession, to marry him ceremoniously to the river waters (Fig. 1).

This ceremony on the banks of the Cauvery is one of many instances in Hindu daily and festive life where the elements in general, and water in particular, are shown respect and veneration. The epithet given to the floods as 'The Lady' is particularly interesting, not only because it signifies a curious personification of matter, but also because this aristocratic and feminine title reflects the various levels of significance that water has to the Hindu mind.

First and foremost, this significance is practical. In a hydraulic agriculture like that of the Cauvery basin, water is only available through irrigation. Working on ditches and dams constitutes a considerable part of the agricultural routine, and the importance of water as the decisive factor in the cycles of food production is constantly evident. Moreover, irrigated water carries nutrition to the fields, which are never artificially fertilised, and this again helps to keep the peasant conscious of the vital importance of water. 'The Lady', then, is primarily an allusion to fecundity, to female procreative energy.

But like so many elementary phenomena in nature, water also has a definite metaphysical significance. In Brahmanical philosophy it stands for the Absolute, an analogy founded in the physical properties of the element: it cannot be grasped, it can take many forms and it pervades everything. This metaphysical significance is reflected in the practice of the daily rituals, which oblige a Brahmin householder to bathe three times a day while performing a complex sequence of rites. The practice is widely followed all over India; there is no sunrise without at least one or two Brahmins within view performing the routine with whatever water they can procure, and in the holy cities many thousands plunge into the rivers. There are a number of scholastic explanations for these rites, the most popular being that the ablutions wash away all contamination inevitably contracted in a householder's life; i.e. the ritual is essen-

tial to protect and preserve life, both in this and in possible future existences. In this context, when water is spoken of as 'The Lady', the Great Protectress is addressed, the nursing and sheltering female, not the procreating one. Every morning when the Brahmins pray their *sandhyas*, they ceremoniously recollect this aspect in the lines of the third stanza:

*O Water! . . . you have the bowels of a mother for us!
I call upon you with the same confidence with which a
child at the approach of danger flies into the arms of a
loving mother!²*

The enormous metaphysical and ritual importance of water in India adds a distinct flavour to Indian riverside scenes. There is a continuous coming and going along the waterfront — the peasant taking his buffaloes to water, with the aristocratic Brahmin withdrawn in meditation next to him, and someone mourning over the ashes of a relative with a noisy bunch of boys playing a few yards away. This strange blend of the highest and the lowest, the sad and the merry, the sacred and the profane, is unique to India (Fig. 2).

The waterfront is one of the focal spaces of public life in every Hindu city. It is here that all important events in the life of both the individual and the community take place, and consequently the spatial integration of water is a matter of great importance. As the waterfront is much frequented, it is usually paved with large slabs of stone, and as the water level is often much lower than the settlement, the access to the river is over a long flight of steps. In the larger towns, these flights of steps are of considerable magnitude, and they are then called 'ghats' in Hindi as well as in most other Indian languages³ (Fig. 13).

Ghats are usually equipped with resting platforms, pavilions, and pillared buildings, designed to form an architectural ensemble with the flights of steps. The term then no longer means a haphazard collection of buildings along a waterfront, but a building type distinct in its architectural characteristics and unique to India. This brief survey is an investigation of the different types of ghats, their various locations in urban settlements, and their basic architectural characteristics, without, however, entering upon stylistic or decorative detail.

Ghats are constructed either along rivers or around tanks. Both types can be found all over India, though river ghats are more common in the north, while tank ghats are characteristic of the Deccan and the Tamil country. Hydrographic differences between the northern plains and the southern plateaux have caused

Fig. 1

this uneven distribution. There are very few perennial streams in the south, which depends entirely on rainfall, while the northern rivers are snow fed. Hence the water which is supplied to the northern plains throughout the year from the hill stream has to be retained artificially in the south by means of reservoirs. Nevertheless, the difference between high-water and low-water levels, both along the northern rivers and in the southern tanks, is extreme, due to heavy evaporation in the hot season, and the flood-like rains that follow. This necessitates the construction of steps to secure a convenient access to the water level at all seasons and, the fluctuations being so enormous, the steps are seemingly endless, creating a picturesque and often magnificent architectural ensemble.

Ghats usually have to fulfil various functions simultaneously: they are ceremoniously used on festive occasions, while on ordinary days they are visited for the routine rituals or simply for bathing and refreshment. However, in larger towns and in the sacred cities ghats often serve a specific purpose. They can be bathing ghats with different sections set apart for different castes, cremation ghats for the performance of funeral rites, *utsava* ghats for the celebration of certain aquatic festivals like the *arat*⁴ or the floating festival, or *dhobi* ghats for the washing of garments by the washermen caste. The *dhobi* ghat is architecturally the least pretentious and it is usually located at some distance from the town proper. But all the other types of ghats are most important public spaces in any urban settlement and hence occupy prominent locations in the spatial system of Hindu towns.

Ghats are found in six basic locations, depending on topographical features as well as on the significance the particular sheet of water has to the ritual and daily life of the urban community. In most northern cities, particularly those located on one of the seven sacred rivers, the ghats occupy the entire waterfront (Fig. 3.1). As these settlements are always on the high bank the ghats are very long and steep, and there is no room for a road along the embankment. Usually, as in Mathura and Benares, the main bazaar street runs at a distance of some 50m. parallel to the river, and numerous perpendi-

Fig. 2

Fig. 4

cular lanes lead down to the ghats. This indicates the dominant orientation of the city towards the river, while the bazaar street facilitates communication between the various quarters.

In the sacred cities on the Deccan, like Ujjain or Nasik, this pattern is still discernible though less rigidly observed partly for topographical reasons — the banks are not so steep as on the mighty northern rivers — and partly because the cities are not so populous, leaving more space along the waterfront for bazaars and markets. Usually the ghats, like the cities, are only on one side of the river, and as a rule the right bank is preferred. There are, however, a few exceptions such as Nasik which is located on both banks of the Narmada. Ghats are constructed at intervals along both waterfronts, with the usual perpendicular lanes leading up to the bazaar streets parallel to the river's course, the whole being thus a twin version of the standard pattern. But the most sacred *tirtha*⁵ is a rocky cliff in midstream, which is completely built over with ghats and pavilion structures (Figs. 3.2 and 4).

There are a few cases in northern India where ghats like those on the sacred rivers are constructed around tanks, the best known example being Gobardhan and Pushkar (Figs. 3.3 and 5). The tank at Pushkar in Rajasthan is one of the most sacred in the whole of India, and on the first full moon after the rains people from distant places come here for ablutions. From an architectural point of view the place is similarly unique, since the entire town consists of nothing but rows of ghats with a single bazaar street leading round the tank on three sides. The water is really the centre of the town, and from all sides covered passages lead down to the ghats. Immediately behind the backyards of the houses begins the desert which extends as far as the eye can reach. In Gobardhan near Mathura the arrangement is similar, though less spectacular. But as a rule, ghats around tanks are never as magnificent as those along the northern rivers.

So far we have considered urban layouts where ghats are the actual centre of the city and are located prominently in the spatial system. There are, however, many cities, where the ghats are located at some distance from the built-up area and integrated not spatially but ritually into the urban configuration. A typical example of such an arrangement is Tiruvanamalai on the Tamil Nadu uplands (Figs. 3.4). Here, all important tanks are located on the *pradakshina-patha*⁶ which leads around the town's sacred mountain, with the exception of a tank inside the temple precincts and another one in the suburbs reserved for the floating festival. In fact, the spatial system of Tiruvanamalai and the architectural handling of water is the reverse of Pushkar; there a large tank is the physical centre of the city, here numerous small ones are located around it.

The ghats in Tiruvanamalai are collectively visited on certain festivals only, when the hill is ceremoniously circumambulated. Hence the ghats are not so much the scene of daily meetings, but of the extraordinary events

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in the life of the urban community. This is the case in many other south Indian temple towns where the main ghats are located outside the city, such as in Srirangam or Tirukalikulundram. In Srirangam the ghats are on the river Cauvery (Fig. 3.5) while in Tirukalikulundram they are constructed around a large tank (Fig. 3.6), but in both cases they are connected with the city centre by a long straight ceremonial way. This axis, together with the temple complex at one end and the ghats along the water at the other, is the characteristic Indian equivalent of the European city square: the urban space where typical forms of public life take place. The Indian peculiarity is that the type of space laid out is not so much congregational as processional, a linear arrangement with a rhythmic sequence of thresholds rather than an enclosure with a focal point. Significantly it is the ghats and the water which are the essential elements besides the temple complex.

There are two variations of the locational types described. If the river bed is very shallow and sandy, or if the town is located on the sea shore, the ghats are constructed not next to the water but on the precipitation of the bank or shore line. This can be seen in Rameswaram, on an island in the Gulf of Manar, where the ghats consist of only a few steps leading down to the beach (Fig. 3.7). There are no stone embankments along the water, one reason apart from the technical difficulties of construction being that the sand is needed for Rameswaram's characteristic *puja*, the moulding and veneration of small sand *lingams*.

Another interesting case is Pandharpur in Maharashtra, where the bed of the Bhima river is too wide to be reached by ghats (Fig. 3.8). There is a flight of steps leading down from the high plateau of the city to the sandbanks in the river bed, but these are so far above normal water level that they are only reached in the highest floods. Hence, at some distance in the river bed, artificial islands were constructed with pavilions raised on the top platform, and ritual baths can be taken on the steps reaching down to the water course (Fig. 12).

The architectural characteristics of ghats around tanks or along rivers are similar, though river ghats are usually much larger. The simplest type of ghat is a flight of steps with occasional resting platforms built at regular intervals (Fig. 6). These platforms are used mainly by holy men who spend all day on the waterfront, and also by other people who store their belongings there while bathing or who meet there afterwards for a chat. For their convenience, the platforms are often sheltered from sun and rain by large umbrellas or by some kind of roof supported by a row of pillars. In fact, if we speak of the ghats as a building type, we are really speaking of the architectural varieties of their parasol structures. If the platforms are large enough, one often sees a tree planted in the middle for the same purpose, but usually they are too small to allow enough room for the roots (Fig. 7). In that case, pavilions are erected, and these are the most common forms of ghat buildings to be found. They show all the styles and

Figs. 6-8

Figs. 9-10

Fig. 13

decorative variations of Hindu architecture, and even a superficial survey of their detailing would fill volumes so richly are they adorned — a fact which indicates the prominent place they take among the traditional building types of India (Fig. 8). Often not only the resting platforms but the entire waterfront is shaded by pillared buildings built over the ghats into the water (Fig. 9). These can be single-storeyed pavilions, sometimes long rows of arcades as along the sacred tank around the Golden Temple at Amritsar, or substantial buildings of several storeys with the substructure resting on rows of pillars along the ghats.

The holy men and *sanyasins* who spend all their life on the ghats have created a building type according to their specific needs (Fig. 10). Little square cells are built horizontally into the steps which can be used as meditation platforms in the early morning and late evening, as shelter from the sun during the heat of the day, as a place to sleep at night, and to store the few belongings the *sanyasin* may call his own. In Benares, a great number of these cells along the northern ghats are occupied by athletes who use them as playgrounds for their physical exercises.

All these architectural forms and types are also found along tank ghats, but there is one type of ghat construction reserved for tanks alone. This is a type where the tank as a whole is shaped like an inverted pyramid, and where the facings on all four sides are constructed in the form of steps with each landing projecting by its own width as one descends. This construction is employed wherever the water level is very low, and where it is in continuous fluctuation. It allows very steep gradients on the tank facings, while at the same time permitting a safe and convenient access to the water to a large number of people simultaneously (Fig. 11).

This survey of water in Hindu urban architecture is necessarily brief, but if it has given an idea of the variety in the architectural handling of this element it has served its purpose. It is significant that these riverside ghats, perhaps the most central architectural space in any Hindu town, are an elaboration of a strikingly simple theme — water. In this the urban architecture of India is characteristically Hindu, reflecting the basically monistic outlook of a civilisation which in spite of all refinement and metaphysical speculation never forgot the elementary human experiences of earth, fire and water.

NOTES

1. A form of Vishnu, present in the Srirangam temple as the first of the 108 Vishnu *Kshetras* of India.
2. Quoted from a translation in Abbé Dubois, *Hindu Manners, Customs and Ceremonies*, 3rd ed., Oxford, 1906, p. 251.
3. 'Ghat' literally means 'a mountain pass, a landing place', according to the Hobson Jobson *Glossary of Colloquial Anglo-Indian*, London, 1886.
4. This is the bathing ritual of the image.
5. Literally a ford. The term denotes the sacred places visited by pilgrims.

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6. *Pradakshina-patha* is the term for any circumambulatory passage or path, but in this context it denotes the road leading around the entire settlement.

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Lord Raganathan, the form of Vishnu present in the Srirangam temple, is carried in procession to the Cauvery ghats to marry the river waters.
2. The ghats at Sringeri in Karnataka, with the group on the right feeding the sacred fish of the Tunga river, the Brahmin in the centre taking his ritual bath, and the lady on the left washing loin cloth.
3. Schematic drawing showing six possible locations of ghats in the urban configuration:
 1. Ghats along the entire waterfront on one bank, as in Benares.
 2. Ghats on both banks of the river, as in Nasik.
 3. Ghats around a large tank in the centre of a town, as in Pushkar.
 4. Ghats around many small tanks located on the *pradakshina-patha*, as in Tiruvanmalai.
 5. Ghats on a river at some distance from the town proper, connected by a ceremonial way.
 6. Ghats around a large tank outside the city, used mainly for aquatic festivals.
 7. Ghats along the sea, located above high-water level.
 8. Ghats leading down into a shallow river bed, where stepped platforms and pavilions are erected next to the water course.
4. Ghats on the midstream cliff in the Narmada at Nasik. The arcades in the background serve as shelter from sun and rain.
5. The sacred tank at Pushkar in Rajasthan, with the town built around it.
6. Octagonal resting platform shaded by a large plaited umbrella.
7. Resting platform sheltered by a tree.
8. Lotus domed pavilion built into the ghats.
9. Arcade built over the ghats, as in Nasik (cf. Fig. 4).
10. Little cubic cells used mainly by holy men living on the ghats.
11. Ghats on the very steep facings of a deep tank, with the landings projecting by their own width as one descends. To the left is a wooden structure built over the ceremonial steps used for the *arat*, the ritual bathing of the image.

Figs. 11-12

12. Stepped platform with a pavilion built near the water course in a very wide, shallow river bed, as in Pandharpur, Maharashtra.
13. The busy ghats at Badami on the Deccan. As there are no public squares in traditional Indian cities, the ghats are, next to the ritual spaces, the location of Hind public life.

All drawings and photographs by the author.

Fig. 5